

Need a New Way to Decide What is Trustworthy

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“There was a Fatwa in Saudi Arabia that men can eat their wives if hungry” if anyone was to come and tell you this, implying that men in Saudi Arabia have the legal and religious sanction to kill and eat their wives if they are hungry, would you believe it? Hopefully not! But one of India’s leading news networks fell for this piece of ‘fake news’ and flashed it as real news.

Similarly, Times Now channel fell for the ‘fake news’ of a rate card doing rounds that there was a cash offer from a militant, Muslim organisation to convert Hindu girls, the “offered rate” for converting a Hindu Brahmin girl was five lakhs, while seven lacs rupees was offered for a Sikh Punjabi girl.

This, in no way reflects some falling standards of media, but actually points to pervasiveness of a social phenomenon that is being witnessed worldwide.

The Phenomenon of ‘Fake News’

Simply put, ‘fake news’ are false stories, often of a sensational nature, that appear to be news, and are spread on the internet or using other media, usually created to influence views or as a joke. While they are created to be widely

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shared online, the purpose for which they are created, could range from that of generating advertisement revenue via web traffic or discrediting a public figure, political movement, or an entity, or even creating a public sentiment or social thought.

It was way back in 1938 that Orson Welles broadcasted a story that armed Martians were invading New Jersey. Welles' brilliantly spun radio broadcast of *The War of the Worlds* created a widespread panic, with the newspapers too, picking up the story. The next morning, Welles did apologize, and clarified that his broadcast was a prank, to prove that Americans could be convinced of anything, even a story as preposterous as armed Martians, and thus it did not perpetuate.

But today, the scenario of 'fake news' has evolved a long way from that. Virulence and the ease of spreading 'fake news' is posing a danger to society and the new social order created by technology is disrupting the way society thinks, gets information and believes and acts.

'Information' is a major power and control centre and the explosion of new ways of dissemination of information has changed the paradigm of how society collects, screens, and disseminates information. A disrupted power centre implies social upheaval with new centres jostling for power, spaces being demarcated, and new power centres being created. That ripple of disturbance caused by technology that has broken the existing information hierarchy in the society that was a major power centre is also of major importance while we are discussing the 'hoo-ha' around 'fake news'.

'Fake News' Problem Multifaceted

Firstly, there are creators of 'fake news'. There are now people and organisations that exploit the gullibility of unsuspecting audiences by 'fake news', for example, in the run-up to the US presidential elections in 2016, a made-up story spread on social media claimed that a paedophile ring involving high-profile members of the Democratic Party was operating out of the basement of a pizza restaurant in Washington DC. In early December 2017, a man walked into the restaurant – which by the way, did not have a basement – and fired an assault rifle. He had expected to find children or their remains in the basement. Remarkably, no one was hurt. But it proves that the effect and impact of misinformation can never be underestimated.

An exclusive IPSOS poll conducted in 2016 for 'BuzzFeed' News found that 75 per cent of American adults viewed a 'fake news' headline as accurate, especially the people who cite Facebook as a major source of their news. In

fact, a global debate around the phenomenon of ‘fake news’ has exploded at a world level since the election of Donald Trump as the US president.

The impact of ‘fake news’ in the American presidential elections and even the Brexit voting brought to fore the danger of manipulation of the masses. As a consequence, questions around the veracity and authenticity of journalism – what journalism is, in the digital age and how we can distinguish it from non-journalism or ‘fake news’ has risen to the top of public, political and scholarly research agendas.

Studies on multiple aspects of the impact of social media, spread of ‘fake news’, creation of ‘fake news’, gullibility in believing the ‘fake news’, business models of ‘fake news’, the ways to fight it, etc. have all been initiated and discussed in America. With the super speed with which the rest of the world is being digitalized, India, too has been ensnared in this ‘fake news’ web.

Secondly, the impact of the ‘fake news’ is to be noted. The stakes are higher than just journalism, elections and making someone the most powerful person in society. What it opens up is another more dangerous vista; the proverbial can of worms. The world social order is stacked on the assumption that every single person is capable of making an informed, logical decision about the society, and hence, the ‘one person- one vote’ principle is being advocated as the best form of representative governance. However, ‘fake news’ has hit at this very core of democracy and thus indirectly questioned the stable world order of “informed decision”. Now the question arises, “if a person is misinformed, or misled to believe something incorrect, will or can democracy and the social order as we know it, still survive?”

This is the main crux of the problem and the reason why everyone is up in arms about ‘fake news’. Thus, having a large number of people in a society who are misinformed or disinformed is absolutely devastating, disruptive and dangerous for the society, itself.

Thirdly, it has also been brought to fore, the question of how the internet has completely changed the paradigm of how the society receives, distributes and consumes information and news, whether true or fake news.

There is a breakdown in the information from trusted sources of information, namely the established media houses who swore by ethical practices, ensured accuracy and verified news before creating information and distributing it to a larger audience. With the increasing reach of the internet and social media, the information paradigm is irrevocably disrupted and any one (whether trusted or not) can be an information creator and distributor.

While the idea of digitalized India is welcomed, and it is true that it has revolutionised many a sector, from tender allocations to revenue departments, from delivering medical aid to conducting educational classes, it should also be remembered that it has also heralded an era where we are literally in deep digitalized waters without knowing how to swim properly, without a life jacket and utterly unaware of the life-threatening dangers lurking around.

The digital invasion has completely changed the way we are living. We are now getting access to some fantastic things that we never thought of, like reading great international authors, getting exposed to new trends, knowing about successful innovations anywhere in the world, hearing the best music ever, finding like-minded people, connecting with them, communicating with our friends and relations not just across the country but across the world. But it is also making some of us very sick. Children are being lured to mutilate and kill themselves.

So, fourthly, it brings us to the question of who we are letting into our lives, mind and personal space with all these digital innovations. In the past, in the era before digitalisation, strangers, whose intentions and agendas were not clear were never welcome in our houses or societies; people had to prove through action and words, to be accepted as leaders who we could believe and follow. Now, however, whatever search engines throw up is considered as correct and believable and complete strangers, who may actually be predators are being accepted as the ultimate truth and are allowed to influence many of our important life decisions!

What it really means is that anyone can say anything, and make you believe in it, with the help of technology. The difference that social media has made is the scale and the ability to find others who share your world view. It will create bubbles of alternative reality, where you are connected to people who are sharing things with you that are equally false, but the cumulative action of all the people sharing fake things create an environment where others are snared into, believing the false things to be true. Any attempt to break through these bubbles are rejected and dismissed as being part of a conspiracy to enforce a “wrong” point of view!

This self-reinforcing bubble is supplemented by technology and algorithms that constantly watch what you are reading, and supplement you with similar material, thus expanding the bubble and creating an exaggerated “echo chamber” effect. Thus, what is to be noted is that from someone verifying and choosing what we are informed about, now information, is verified, biased, slanted, manipulated, falsified, baiting in nature, bigoted, etc., and spreads around the world in seconds, with the potential of reaching billions of people in mere

seconds. On the other end of the spectrum, due to the information explosion, lots of information, which may have a lot of potential for good, is also dismissed with a flick of the finger.

What information we choose to consume, whom we choose to engage with is self-reinforcing and we are shown more of the same. The space for a contradictory point of view is minimizing. What we believe is correct, and we keep connecting with people on the net, who believe in what we do, rather than talking to people around us, weighing both sides of an argument and giving acceptance and space to an opposing point of view.

Fifth point to ponder is who is accessing all this wealth of information that is so easily available and what use are they are putting it to? For example, a boy in Florida who slaughtered 14 of his classmates and three of his teachers spent months telling a private ‘Instagram®’ group that black people and Mexicans should be kept in chains and that white women who married African-Americans had committed treason. He had been insisting that he had been possessed by a demon who was urging him to “Burn. Destroy. Kill.” We need to explain to the digital netizens that life is not a role-playing game.

The combined effect of all this is that, while we surf up in this digitalized world, we “feel” safe. So, we let go of a lot of our apprehensions and thus we believe in what we see on the net. That is the reason why we see false messages about child kidnappers going viral on ‘WhatsApp’, prompting fearful mobs to kill two dozen innocent people.

It did awaken the Indian society to the impact of dangers of digital ‘fake news’ on society. “That something being forwarded on the net” has taken control of people’s minds, is feeding on their insecurities and making them react out of proportion of an artificially created fear. The multiple mob lynching incidents across the country, that took a toll of more than 28 people made the government sit up, and also drew sharp reactions from the Supreme Court. The government then slapped the messaging platform ‘WhatsApp’ with two notices, in August 2018, with the second one warning the platform that it will treat the messaging platform as an ‘abettor’ of rumour propagation and legal consequences will follow, if adequate checks were not put in place. ‘WhatsApp’ has responded to the Indian government’s actions by limiting the number of forwards to 5, but is that really adequate? Given the stakes and motivations involved in creating and spreading ‘fake news’, the answer seems to be a ‘Woeful No’!

The world over, governments are taking notice of this problem, the British Parliament too has set up a committee to discuss the issue of how social media

is being misused by some to misinform and potentially incite. The internet, with its free and open nature, has rapidly grown in the last decade-and-a-half and touched everything from consumer lives to governments. The Internet, today, to many is intermediated through various platforms like Facebook, Google, ‘WhatsApp’ and other messenger apps that all sit on the internet and collectively either constitute messaging, or search functionalities, to consumers.

The paradox is that, while we want government action, we also fiercely want to safeguard our right to freedom of expression and do not want the governments to restrict that. We do not want governments to restrict or curtail the freedom to use these apps or the internet services. The technology giants are refusing to hand over the encryption codes to authorities, as it would lead to breaching of privacy and the governments could easily snoop on the activity of any citizen. So, the fight that should focus on apprehending the perpetrators or spreaders of the ‘fake news’, is being shifted to various other unrelated factors.

The fight against ‘fake news’ is made more complex by the fact that the ‘fake news’ going around in the city differs, based on purpose content, and intention.

Types of Fake News

We can say that broadly speaking, there are two kinds of ‘fake news’, based on content:

1. False stories that are made up deliberately, where the creator knows that the content is false, but still creates/ publishes it. These are deliberate lies that are put online, even though the person writing them knows that they are made up.
2. Then, there are stories that *may* have some truth to them, but are not completely accurate. This is because the people writing them - for example, journalists or bloggers - don’t check *all* of the facts before publishing the story, or they might exaggerate some of it, or may have been lured into believing what they are publishing is the truth.

For example, the news broadcasted by Aajtak, and Times Now, mentioned earlier fall in this second category. Here, the intention is not to mislead or to disinform. So naturally, additional diligence before publishing, especially by news agencies, is one of the solutions to fight the ‘fake news’ problem.

More challenging is the ‘fake news’ that is made viral, knowing that it is ‘fake’. Broadly, speaking, this news is created to spread misinformation to propagate a political/social view, or for monetization, to earn from clicks. With

easily available and free technology on the net, it is also much easier than it used to be to edit photos, and create fake websites and stories that look realistic.

Moreover, misleading and sensational headings with raunchy photographs still act as click baits i.e. they attract the surfer's attention and they click on these headlines to know more.

It is these kinds of messages that create the menace of 'fake news'; moreover, the problem is compounded by people who keep on forwarding these messages. Simply speaking, people also tend to share things that they agree with, feel they are the first to share, or have received it from someone they trust.

This compounds the problem and is one of the reasons why even after a 'fake news' is busted, i.e. proven fake, the correction does not go viral.

One example of this, that Paul Resnick, of the University of Michigan and his team, investigating the impact of 'fake news', found, was a mistake that appeared in a leaked draft of a World Health Organisation (WHO) report that stated many people in Greece who had HIV had infected themselves in an attempt to get welfare benefits. The WHO put out a correction, but even so, the initial mistake reached far more people than the correction did. Another example is the recent rumour about the death of former Prime Minister of India Atal Bihari Vajpayee, which had the government issuing statements about his health status.

Whatever, may be the reason, it is a fact that people do forward stories that they are not sure of; they also forward photos they may have not clicked; and they forward slanderous material, just because it is funny, i.e. people, (including you and me), forward stories that we have not verified.

So, the "citizen journalists" themselves get duped, and act as agents of the duper as they get sucked into a digital bubble that is actually completely different to the real world – and a long way from the truth.

An entirely new element is added to the 'fake news' rhetoric, when the so called 'fake news' turns out to be, not really 'fake news'! Sometimes, a story might be branded as 'fake' (when actually it isn't) by someone, or a group of people, who do not want to accept that the news is true – even if it might be. This is one of the reasons why many groups are now actually questioning the credibility of media. Any negative news, (or news that reflects a different view from the one they wish to propagate) which may actually be true is dismissed as 'fake' by these people, just because they do not want it to be true. These ideologically motivated people will call something 'fake news', when it is not really, and this leads to the fact that some people do not know what to believe anymore. This has ultimately resulted in creating doubts in the minds of people

about the authenticity and the credibility of traditional media, and even scientific reports and study. The traditional watchdogs and safeguards put in place to ensure that those in power are honest, are being circumvented by the social media.

This is supported by the fact that in today's world, people do not agree with official sources of information at all. Governments and media around the world are facing increasing scepticism about what they are giving out as information, and thus, alternative sources of information are getting strongholds as "sharing right information." This has led to a vicious circle of information and misinformation or disinformation. Facebook has been used by political bodies to put out information, pay for advertising, put it in front of millions of people. What is worrisome is that those who are not being targeted by these advertisements will not even know about such a massive information campaign going on, and the changing scenario around them.

In the era of digital marketing, anyone can target people based on how old they are, where they live, what skin colour they have, what gender they are, what they usually surf about, who are their connects etc. We should not think of social media as just a peer-to-peer communication – it is also "the most powerful advertising platform there has ever been."

Thus, social media is no longer just a peer-to-peer communication; it now also has the most powerful advertising platform which can be used to change or create rhetoric, that can and will finally change the social dialogue, as it is easy to spend money and advertise to influence millions of people and not have the other millions of notice.

Just as the problem of 'fake news' is manifold, the solution to fight the menace of 'fake news' is also manifold. For those leading the push to fact-check information, technological interventions like better tagging of accurate information, adding layers of credibility to sources, disrupting business models of click-baits, improving algorithms to crack 'fake news' offenders and improve black-list offenders are on the anvil.

Another part of the solution would be providing people with the resources to fact-check information for themselves. Many initiatives like Google News Initiative by Google, firstdraft.com by Harvard University, etc. are working to develop awareness about the free resources available on the net to help individual and professional fact-checkers to cross check information.

Twitter and Facebook both insist they have strict rules on what can be advertised and particularly on political advertising.

While there is lot of pressure of digital platforms like Facebook, Google, WhatsApp, Snapchat, Instagram, etc to come up with solutions, the fact of the matter is that there is no quick-fix ‘tech solution’ to this problem, simply because, the ‘fake news’ problem is not simple but rather complex and multi-faceted.

Expecting engineers to come up with solutions overnight, is trivializing the issue and a very crucial, negative element in the ‘fake news’ phenomenon. Basically because, “techies” cannot create algorithms that will teach machines to decide what is true or false in a world where humans themselves do not agree as to what is true and what is not.

The problem in tackling the ‘fake news’ menace is not just combating with a few malicious ‘bots’ or chaos-loving trolls or even money-oriented teenagers pushing phony stories for clicks and thus profit. The problem is also the gullible readers.

‘Fake news’ is ‘fake’ but it gets viral because it promises otherwise. Can ‘fake news’ create an alternative reality just by reinforcing it? It also throws up philosophical questions like who define the truth, and what is the truth? The major upheaval caused by technology is that Truth as dictated by a “powerful few” has ceased to exist, and rather, truth is what is networked by and among peers. So, for every fact put out by someone, there is a counter fact. All those counter facts and facts look identical online, which is confusing to most people, and they tend to believe those people who are reaching out to them through the social media. Most people, who are under the onslaught of social media, do not have the time to cross verify the information, and they tend to believe mostly those people who they are in contact with, irrespective of the veracity of the facts.

Thus, ‘WhatsApp’, in its response to government notices, has now, actually taken some initiatives to curb this type of a ‘fake news’ circulation, outlining new rules and regulations to hopefully curb the menace of misinformation by including education and some form of advocacy efforts. While technology can help, education, awareness, and finally action by the end users is the only cure to fight the menace of ‘fake news’. More challenging is the attitude of some people, who feel that ‘fake news’ are by “others” and as people or society, they themselves will not be affected. This is an absolute fallacy. Every user, who forwards a story, is impersonating as a journalist. Thus, every forward should be done diligently.

There are very simple tools that are freely available on the internet that one can employ to weed out ‘fake news’. One can do a reverse image search of

Google, use other search engines like ‘Yandex’ or ‘Tinyye’ search, even break down collages to search for images, take screenshots of videos to ensure image search, etc.

A look at the original source of information and checking its credibility is the most crucial of all other parameters. For example, Wikipedia which many youngsters use as an online reference, can be edited by anyone and uses teams of volunteer editors to weed out inaccuracies – is far from perfect. Inaccurate information is a regular feature on the website and requires careful cross-checking for anyone wanting to use it.

There are also mirror websites that pretend to be the real one. For example, we have come across many “free offers” from Google. It is important to check the extension. The name just before the dot is important, like google.com is correct, while <google.freeoffer.com> is a fake website.

Above all, one should let basic journalistic sense and scepticism prevail. One must understand the context, connect the impact of a message, and ask oneself basic questions like, ‘Is this plausible? ... Who is saying this? ... What will be the impact? ... Are a lot of people talking about it? ... Is credible media talking about it? ... Which organisations have published the story? ... Does the story *sound* believable? ... etc. If the answer to any of these questions is ‘no’, then it requires a further check, a reality check before forwarding and spreading the word.

Moreover, keeping an open mind and developing critical thinking skills is the key to overcoming the phenomenon of ‘fake news’. It will help overcome the bias in the way people understand the world in a language in which they tend to seek and accept information which confirms to their existing beliefs, while rejecting information that contradicts those beliefs.

To conclude, one can say that the way the young adults are consuming news, it may make the traditional media services and agencies less relevant, and sometimes, even end up making the ‘fake news’ more real than the actual real news programs. Concern over this problem is now becoming universal with global proportions and ramifications. However, much remains unknown regarding the vulnerabilities of individuals, institutions, and society to the manipulations by such malicious actors.

A new system of safeguards has now become necessary to combat this evil. We need a new way to decide what is trustworthy. We need to recreate a system at this stage, of whom to believe in, not just what to believe in.

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